

Quality Control Assessment and Biodistribution of Indigenously Developed $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA) During Initial Clinical Assessment as a Potential Imaging Agent for Prostate Cancer

Vandana Kumar Dhingra

Department of Nuclear Medicine, AIIMS Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, India

Meena Negi

Department of Nuclear Medicine, AIIMS Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, India

Puja Panwar Hazari

*Division of Cyclotron and Division of Radiopharmaceutical Science,
INMAS, DRDO, Delhi, India*

Sandip Basu

RMC, HBNU, TMH Annexe, Parel, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Anil K. Mishra

Department of Chemistry, IIT, Roorkee, Uttarakhand, India

Ankur Mittal

Department of Urology, AIIMS Rishikesh, India

Manoj Kumar Gupta

Department of Radiation Oncology, AIIMS Rishikesh, India

Suggested Citation

Dhingra, V.K., Negi, M., Hazari, P.P., Basu, S., Mishra, A.K., Mittal, A., & Gupta, M.K. (2024). Quality Control Assessment and Biodistribution of Indigenously Developed $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA) During Initial Clinical Assessment as a Potential Imaging Agent for Prostate Cancer. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 914-923. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).80](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).80)

Abstract:

Introduction: SPECT and PET radiopharmaceuticals have been used in early diagnosis of prostate cancer. C-11 methionine is a PET tracer but it is expensive and not widely available in many centres. SPECT-based tracer $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis (ChoEA) has shown promising results with brain tumor imaging. The uptake of $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis (ChoEA) is facilitated by the up-regulation of amino acid transporters which has been observed in many tumor cells to facilitate these accelerated rates of amino acid uptake. It is readily available at low cost and could possibly have potential for detection of prostate cancer. Aim of the study: To assess quality control and biodistribution of indigenously developed $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis (ChoEA) during initial clinical assessment in patients with prostate cancer. **Objectives of the study:** To study the physiological uptake

of radiolabeled amino acids $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA) in patients with known carcinoma prostate and evaluate the labelling efficiency of indigenously prepared $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA) kits. **Results:** A total of 15 patients were included in our study. Physiological uptake of tracer $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA) was seen in liver, kidneys and blood pool in visual inspection. The tracer uptake was maximum at 1 hour and gradually reduces over next 3 hours. A total of 15 patients with carcinoma prostate were available for evaluation with $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]$ DTPA-bis(ChoEA). This showed significant choline biodistribution at 1hr with mean liver uptake: Bkg (background) ratio of (7.7 ± 2.97) & kidney uptake: Bkg ratio of (6.6 ± 0.14)

in whole body imaging. Biodistribution of this tracer and its labelling efficiency on the scans was found to be satisfactory in all patients. **Conclusion:** This is the first study done for assessment of $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$ in patients with prostate cancer. The radiochemical purity of ^{99m}Tc - choline was nearly ~97% which was in the acceptable range with physiological tracer uptake was seen in kidneys, liver and blood pool.

Keywords: *Quality Control, $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$, Prostate Cancer, Biodistribution, SPECT.*

Introduction

Nuclear Medicine involves internally administered radioactive tracers followed by imaging for diagnosis, as well as for therapeutics purposes (theranostics). Radiopharmaceuticals are crucial in nuclear medicine imaging, where a radioactive isotope is combined with a chemical compound to produce detailed images of internal body processes. Ensuring the quality of these radiotracers is essential to confirm their potency, purity, and safety before administration to patients. This includes assessing factors like radiolabeling, biodistribution, and performing physical, physiochemical, and biological tests. Thus, quality control of radioactive tracer is one of the important parameters for checking overall quality performance in nuclear medicine imaging which shows the assurance of the tracer whether it is administered to the patient or not and checking the purity of the radiopharmaceutical and radionuclide to ensure optimum imaging results and patient safety (Saha, 2004).

Prostate malignancy has always been an area for novel research and advancement, this is due to a long life expectancy of more than two decades in these men. In past two decades, there is an increase in incidence rate of prostate cancer in men. This has further led to a demand in improving quality of life of these patients with better diagnostic and therapeutic modalities.

Amino acids are essential not only for protein synthesis but also as carbon and nitrogen sources in the synthesis of purine and pyrimidine nucleotides, amino sugars, and glutathione. Continuously proliferating tumor cells have a unique metabolic need for amino acids to support their continuous division and uncontrolled growth. The up-regulation of amino acid transporters has been observed in

many tumor cells to facilitate these accelerated rates of amino acid uptake. Amino acid-based imaging probes are proposed to target up-regulated amino acid transporters in tumor cells (Nelson, & Cox, 2008; van Lith, et al., 2022).

Different radiopharmaceuticals were used for prostate imaging. Indium-111 (In-111) capromab pentetide (ProstaScint®) was the earliest FDA-approved PSMA-ligand radiotracer. But, due to long half-life of radionuclide, delayed imaging is mainly preferred (30 min, and between 72 and 120 h) which is the disadvantage of this tracer.

In recent years, the role of nuclear medicine for detection and staging of prostate cancer has emerged rapidly due to the development of novel imaging agents- (1) Carbon-11 Choline (C-11 Choline)- first approved in 2012 by the Food and Drug administration (FDA) for imaging men with a biochemical recurrence of prostate cancer (2) Fluorine-18 Fluciclovine (Axumin) was approved by the FDA in May of 2016 for the same indication (3) Gallium-68 PSMA-11 (Ga-68 PSMA-11, Illuccix, Locametz) FDA approved, continued on prostate-targeted PET agents, and in December of 2020, the FDA approved (Volpe, et al., 2023).

There is a need for the development of new tracer which is used for diagnostic as well as therapeutic purpose. PET/CT Imaging is not widely available in many centres due to expensive technology. Thus it is imperative to develop new SPECT tracers because of its easy availability and cost effectiveness.

Recently, the advent of theranostic pairs for carcinoma prostate has emerged and have been used for treatment of prostate malignancy. Here one tracer is used for imaging (Ga-68 labelled

PSMA) and a therapeutic radioisotope (alpha or beta emitters) with similar ligand (Lu-177 PSMA) is used for targeting the lesions seen on the diagnostic scans. This molecularly targeted radiotherapy has lesser side effects and is liable for repeat therapy in multiple sessions (Young, n.d.). Development of new SPECT diagnostic tracers (like amino acids) would also add to potential for development of new theranostic pairs.

Aim of the Study

To assess quality control and biodistribution of indigenously developed $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis}(\text{ChoEA})$ agent for prostate cancer.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the physiological uptake of radiolabeled amino acids $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis}(\text{ChoEA})$ in patients with known carcinoma prostate
- To study the labelling efficiency of indigenously prepared $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis}(\text{ChoEA})$ kits.

Materials and Methods

Equipment

- Dual head SPECT/CT- NM CT 670 with large field of view fitted with a low energy high resolution collimator
- $^{99}\text{Mo-}^{99m}\text{Tc}$ Generator (Figure1).

Materials Required

For elution of $^{99}\text{Mo-}^{99m}\text{Tc}$ Generator: Saline vial, vacuum vial, lead shielded pot, sterile alcohol swab

Choline kit: This was supplied by Division of Cyclotron & Radiopharmacy, Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences (INMAS), Delhi (Figure 2).

Figure 1. $^{99}\text{Mo-}^{99m}\text{Tc}$ Generator

Figure 2. Choline Kit (Freeze Dried Indigenously Prepared)

For preparation of $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis}(\text{ChoEA})$: Saline (0.91% NaCl) bottle, syringes, needles, Choline kit, Millipore filter (0.22 μm), lead pot, syringe shield

Storage of Choline kit: Deep freezer

Materials required for Quality control of ^{99m}Tc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA): Test tubes, Test

tube stand, syringes, Whatmann paper III, acetone, scissor, , standard source [Cs-137].

Acetone and Whatmann Paper No 3 Strip , well counter (Figure 3,4).

Figure 3. Acetone & Whatmann Paper No.3 Strip

Figure 4. Well Counter & Its Display

Radiopharmaceutical used: [^{99m}Tc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA)

Dosage: For Adults, standard dose is 15-20mCi

Procedure: ^{99}Mo - ^{99m}Tc Generator (Coltech) was available in the Department of Nuclear Medicine. Activity was eluted from ^{99}Mo - ^{99m}Tc

Generator in the form of Sodium Pertechnetate ($^{99m}\text{TcO}_4^-$) with the help of saline and vacuum vial every working day. Before eluting the generator, the top of saline and vacuum vial were cleaned with alcohol swab and the vacuum vial was put inside the shielded lead pot. After this,

the vacuum vial and saline vial were placed on the generator for eluting the activity. The radioactivity was eluted from ^{99}Mo - $^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$ Generator in the form of Sodium Pertechnetate ($^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_4^-$)

Preparation of Radiopharmaceutical: Kits used for [$^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$] DTPA-bis (ChoEA) imaging for clinical studies were assessed for quality of radiolabelling. A total of 15 samples were included in our study. For labelling the radiopharmaceutical, Choline vial was kept outside to attain ambient room temperature. A sterile sodium pertechnetate ($\text{Na}^{99\text{m}}\text{TcO}_4$) with activity 20-25mCi was added to make the

volume to 1.5ml with 0.9% sodium chloride solution and equal volume of air was withdrawn from the vial and mixed it properly. Then the vial was kept for incubation for 20 minutes. After incubation, [$^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$]DTPA-bis(ChoEA) radiopharmaceutical was filtered through Millipore filter with a pore size of $0.22\mu\text{m}$. The filtered radiopharmaceutical was administered to the patients and proper radiation safety protocols were followed while handling the radiopharmaceutical.

Preparation of Radiopharmaceutical [$^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$] DTPA-bis (ChoEA)

Figure 5. Procedure for Preparing [$^{99\text{m}}\text{Tc}$]DTPA-bis(ChoEA) Radiopharmaceutical

Quality control of ^{99m}Tc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA)

Figure 6. Procedure for Assessing Purity (Quality Check) of Radiopharmaceutical

Procedure for Quality Control of Radiopharmaceutical

Before administration of radiopharmaceutical to the patient, first step is to check the purity of radiopharmaceutical whether it is labelled or not. The radiochemical purity test was done by

performing paper chromatography for prepared radiopharmaceuticals. In paper chromatography, stationary phase was Whatmann strip III and mobile phase was acetone (used as solvent). In paper chromatography, a small drop of radiopharmaceutical was putting onto the Whatman strip and run in solvent- acetone.

After the completion of chromatography procedure, strip was taken out from the test tube and dried it. The strip was cut into 2 equal parts and measured into the well counter. Radiochemical purity was then calculated for all

samples. Biodistribution of all samples for quality control was also studied during imaging.

Radiochemical purity (RCP) was calculated as follows.

Figure 7. Chromatography Procedure

Figure 8. Free and Bound Form of Radiopharmaceutical is Present

$$\% \text{ Free fraction } [A] = \frac{A}{A+B} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Bound fraction} = 100 - \% \text{ Free}(A) \quad (2)$$

In this way, the radiochemical purity was calculated for all samples.

Results

Physiological Uptake of $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$ - Qualitatively

Physiological uptake of tracer $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$ was seen in liver, kidneys and blood pool in visual inspection. No thyroid and gastric uptake were seen in all 15 patients and optimum radiolabelling was observed in visual inspection. This showed that all samples were satisfactorily radiolabelled. There is significant hepatobiliary excretion in case of $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$ and the urinary route is the alternate route of excretion. The tracer uptake was imaged at 1 hour and 3 hours. A total of 15 patients with carcinoma prostate were available for evaluation with $[^{99m}\text{Tc}]\text{DTPA-bis(ChoEA)}$. Images showed significant choline biodistribution at 1hr with mean liver uptake: Bkg ratio of (7.7 ± 2.97) & kidney uptake: Bkg ratio of (6.6 ± 0.14) in whole body imaging. Biodistribution of this tracer and its labelling efficiency on the scans was found to be satisfactory in all patients.

Figure 9. Biodistribution of [99mTc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA)

Quantitative Measurement of Radiolabeling Efficiency %

The percentage of radiochemical purity was assessed quantitatively to check the quality of

radiopharmaceuticals before administering to the patients. A bar graph was plotted between percentage of bound fraction & number of samples as shown in Fig.10.

Figure 10. Graph Plot between Percentage of Bound Fraction & Number of Samples

Discussion

F-18 FDG is the workhorse for most solid tumors in oncology, however, unfortunately, in prostate cancer several factors make 18F-FDG less useful than in other tumour types. High excretion through the urinary tract where the prostate is located, and lower avidity of the glucose analog for relatively indolent primary prostate cancers. Usually Prostate cancers which become more aggressive show 18 F-FDG uptake. 11C-choline, 18F-fluoromethylcholine, and 18F-fluoroethylcholine are well known choline derivatives employed for PET imaging. However, PET tracers have shorter half lives and are limited in availability. The synthesized [99mTc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA) moiety possesses favorable characteristics such as water solubility, low toxicity, and high stability requisites and has potential for clinical use as seen in animal models. Pre-clinical SPECT/CT studies with [99mTc]DTPA-bis(ChoEA) were well supported by in vitro cell binding and ex vivo biodistribution experiments. The radioactivity accumulation at the tumor site was quite significant as compared to the contralateral tissue. This is the first clinical study involving [99mTc] DTPA-bis (ChoEA). Labelling efficiency in our study was lesser (99% versus 97%) but acceptable and comparable to the initial preclinical study by the same co-investigators, this could be due to storage and transport related factors. Physiological uptake of liver and kidneys (routes of excretion) as well as biodistribution were comparable and acceptable to the initial study (Jaswal, et al., 2022).

The most recently used prostate imaging radiopharmaceuticals are Tc-99m PSMA, C-11 Choline, F-18 Fluciclovine, and F-18 PSMA which are mainly used for PET and SPECT imaging. Tc-99m PSMA (Prostate-Specific Membrane Antigen): This targets the prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA), a protein highly expressed on prostate cancer cells mainly in advanced disease. The highest uptake is in prostate cancer lesions (especially in high-grade or metastatic disease) and there is minimal background activity in normal tissues compared to F-18 PSMA and C-11 Choline. The physiological uptake of this tracer is bladder

organ which cause imaging artifacts. Due to less expensive and easy availability, this tracer has high potential for detecting distant metastasis in prostate cancer. F-18 PSMA is a PET radiopharmaceutical that targets prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA), a protein highly expressed in prostate cancer cells, especially in advanced or metastatic disease. It has high sensitivity for detecting metastases in prostate cancer especially staging and restaging (Jaswal, et al., 2022; Vyas, Henderson, & Leslie, 2023).

F-18 Fluciclovine is an amino acid analog that targets L amino acid transporter system, which are overexpressed in prostate cancer cells especially in recurrent disease. It has higher uptake in prostate cancer cells, particularly in recurrent prostate cancer, and is effective even in cases of PSA recurrence (Vyas, Henderson, & Leslie, 2023).

C-11 Choline is used to detect prostate cancer by targeting cell membrane phospholipid metabolism (specifically, choline kinase activity), which is upregulated in prostate cancer cells. High uptake of C-11 Choline in prostate cancer tissue due to increased choline metabolism in tumor cells. It is less sensitive for bony metastases disease and high sensitivity for soft tissue metastasis. So, it has the potential to detect prostate cancer in early diagnosis. Due to C-11 short half-life $t_{1/2} = 20\text{min}$ and requirement of in-house cyclotron facility, it has limited use in routine clinical practice. So, [99mTc] DTPA-bis (ChoEA) as a potential tool for early detection of prostate cancer was explored in this study with potential advantages of indigenous preparation, less radiation burden as its half-life 6hrs, energy = 140KeV and easy availability. The uptake mechanism of C-11 choline is similar with [99mTc] DTPA-bis (ChoEA). Biodistribution of C-11 Choline has been seen mainly in the renal cortex, salivary glands, liver, spleen, pancreas, blood and muscle. This pattern of biodistribution is similar for [99mTc] DTPA-bis (ChoEA) found in our study as well (Smith, et al., 2019; Wibmer, et al., 2016).

Conclusion

To our knowledge this is the first study done for assessment of quality control and biodistribution of [^{99m}Tc] DTPA-bis(ChoEA) in multiple human subjects. The radiochemical purity of ^{99m}Tc- Choline was nearly ~97% which was in the acceptable range with physiological tracer uptake was seen in kidneys, liver and blood pool. This new SPECT amino acid tracer agent may be have potential for molecular imaging of various cancers especially prostate cancer.

Conflict of Interest Statement

All authors declare no conflict of interest in the above work.

Ethical Approval Statement

The study was performed after ethical approval from IEC, vide ref No: AIIMS/IEC/18/461

Acknowledgements

- i. Executive Director & CEO, AIIMS Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, India
- ii. Director, INMAS, DRDO, Delhi, India

References

Jaswal, A. P., Hazari, P. P., Prakash, S., Sethi, P., Kaushik, A., Roy, B. G., Kathait, S., Singh, B., & Mishra, A. K. (2022). [^{99m}Tc]Tc-DTPA-Bis(cholineethylamine) as an oncologic tracer for the detection of choline transporter (ChT) and choline kinase (ChK) expression in cancer. *ACS Omega*, 7(15), 12509–12523. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c04256>

Nelson, D. L., & Cox, M. M. (2008). *Lehninger principles of biochemistry* (5th ed.). W. H. Freeman.

Saha, G. B. (2004). *Fundamentals of nuclear pharmacy* (5th ed.). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-2934-4>

Smith, C. P., Laucis, A., Harmon, S., Mena, E., Lindenberg, L., Choyke, P. L., & Turkbey, B. (2019). Novel imaging in detection of metastatic prostate cancer. *Current Oncology Reports*, 21, 1–9.

Tolvanen, T., Yli-Kerttula, T., Ujula, T., Autio, A., Lehtikoinen, P., Minn, H., & Roivainen, A. (2010). Biodistribution and radiation dosimetry of [(11)C]choline: A comparison between rat and human data. *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging*, 37(5), 874–883. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00259-009-1346-z>

van Lith, S. A. M., Raave, R., et al. (2022). Amino acid transport: Basic concepts, radiopharmacy, and instrumentation. *Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging*.

Volpe, F., Nappi, C., Piscopo, L., Zampella, E., Mainolfi, C. G., Ponsiglione, A., Imbriaco, M., Cuocolo, A., & Klain, M. (2023). Emerging role of nuclear medicine in prostate cancer: Current state and future perspectives. *Cancers*, 15(19), 4746.

Vyas, M., Henderson, A., & Leslie, S. (2023). Nuclear medicine applications in prostate cancer. *StatPearls*.

Wibmer, A. G., Burger, I. A., Sala, E., Hricak, H., Weber, W. A., & Vargas, H. A. (2016). Molecular imaging of prostate cancer. *Radiographics*, 36(1), 142–159.

Young, J. D. (n.d.). *Imaging and therapeutic radiotracers for prostate cancer* (Doctoral dissertation, King's College London).